

Which process of heat transfer cools a cup of hot beverage – the answer isn't conduction, convection or radiation

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Abstract

There are three commonly considered processes of heat transfer, namely, conduction, convection and radiation. But the cooling of a hot beverage does not take place through any of the above processes - it is mostly through the process of vaporization. We have estimated the order of magnitude of the heat lost for different processes and compared them to arrive at the above conclusion.

1 Introduction

For our study, we consider a cup of hot beverage without a lid, i.e., one surface of the liquid is exposed to the atmosphere. Since most hot beverages are either solutions or suspensions with water as the solvent, we shall assume some properties of water for our calculations.

Thermal flux(q'') is the flow of heat per unit area per unit time. We shall estimate the order of magnitude of the thermal flux for different processes of heat transfer and compare them to deduce the process that causes the highest amount of heat loss.

2 Heat lost through convection

The basic equation for convective heat transfer is given by[2]

$$q''_{cv} = h_c \Delta T \quad (1)$$

Where h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient, ΔT is the temperature difference between the liquid and the surroundings.

The heat transfer coefficient for air can be approximated by the empirical equation[3]

$$h_c = 12.12 - 1.16v + 11.6\sqrt{v} \quad (2)$$

Where v is the velocity of wind in contact with the surface and v , h_c are in SI units. The above equation is valid for wind velocities upto 20 ms^{-1} only. Therefore, the order of $h_c \sim 10^1 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$.

Since most beverages have water as the solvent and the boiling point of water is 373.15K , the temperature difference between the liquid and the surroundings is of the order of $\Delta T \sim 10^1\text{K}$. Impurities can cause small changes in the boiling point of water but the order of magnitude shall remain unchanged.

Thus, the order of thermal flux turns out to be $q''_{cv} \sim 10^2 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$.

3 Heat lost through radiation

Stefan-Boltzmann law for the power radiated from a black body in terms of its temperature is given by[7]

$$q''_{rad} = \epsilon\sigma(T^4 - T_0^4) \quad (3)$$

Where ϵ is the emissivity of the vessel, σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant of value $5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-4}$, T is the temperature of the liquid and T_0 is the surrounding temperature.

The emissivity is always less than 1, which would imply, $\epsilon \sim 10^{-1}$.

Taking $T = 373\text{K}$ (boiling point of water) and $T = 300\text{K}$ (room temperature), $(T^4 - T_0^4) = 1.13 \times 10^{10} \text{ K}^4$.

Thus, the order of thermal flux turns out to be $q''_{rad} \sim 10^1 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$.

4 Heat lost through conduction

Fourier's law for conductive heat transfer is given by[4]

$$q'' = -k\nabla T \quad (4)$$

Where k is the thermal conductivity, ∇T is the temperature gradient. The negative sign shows that heat flux moves from higher temperature regions to lower temperature regions.

Since we are considering heat loss, we can write

$$q''_{cd} = k\nabla T \quad (5)$$

The heat loss is maximised when the material of the vessel is not an insulator. Let us consider the worst-case scenario that the vessel acts as a diathermal wall, i.e., the surface of the vessel is at the same temperature as the liquid inside.

The thermal conductivity of air in the range $388-498 \text{ K}$ is $0.03 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. [6]

The thermal gradient of air is of the order $\nabla T \sim 10^1 \text{ Km}^{-1}$. [5]

Thus, the order of thermal flux turns out to be $q''_{cd} \sim 10^{-1} \text{ Wm}^{-2}$.

It can be argued that the bottom of the vessel is in contact with the table and we should consider the thermal conductivity of the tabletop for that. But the bottom of the cup does not touch the table. If you look closely at the underside

of any cup, you will see a raised edge along the circumference. The purpose of this edge is to prevent the bottom of the cup from touching the table. This leaves an air gap between the cup and the table. It is this raised edge that is in contact with the table. The area of this thin edge can be neglected compared to the total area of the vessel.

5 Heat lost through vaporization

Vaporization of water from a water surface depends on the water temperature, the surrounding temperature, air humidity and wind velocity above the water surface.[8] The amount of water vaporized per unit area per unit time can be expressed as[9][10]

$$\dot{m} = \frac{h_c}{c_a}(x_n - x_s) \quad (6)$$

Where h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient, c_a is the specific heat of air, x_n is the maximum humidity ratio of saturated air at the ambient temperature and x_s is the humidity ratio of saturated air at the pool temperature.

x_n, x_s are fractions and therefore must be less than 1 ($x_n, x_s \sim 10^{-1}$).

When water evaporates from the exposed surface, it takes away heat from the rest of the liquid.¹ This heat is the mass of water evaporated multiplied by the latent heat of vaporization.

$$q''_{vp} = \dot{m}L = \frac{h_c L}{c_a}(x_n - x_s) \quad (7)$$

¹For all the other processes, the heat is lost through the lateral surfaces of the vessel as well as the exposed surface of the fluid. However, that is not the case for vaporization which takes place only at the exposed surface. The exposed surface area will surely be lesser than the lateral surface area but there will not be any difference in their orders of magnitude.

The latent heat of vaporization of water is $2.26 \times 10^6 \text{ Jkg}^{-1}$ at atmospheric pressure.[11]

The specific heat capacity of air is of the order $c_a \sim 10^3 \text{ Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$. [12]

Thus, the order of thermal flux turns out to be $q''_{vp} \sim 10^3 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$.

6 Conclusion

The total heat lost through conduction, convection and radiation combined is $Q'' = q''_{cd} + q''_{cv} + q''_{rad} \sim 10^2$. Thus, $q''_{vp} > Q''$. In the previous sections it has been shown that $q''_{vp} > q''_{cv} > q''_{rad} > q''_{cd}$.

This proves that heat lost through vaporization is greater than heat lost through all other processes, namely, conduction, convection, radiation. Further, the heat lost through vaporization is greater than heat lost through all other processes combined ($q''_{vp} > Q''$). The least amount of heat is lost through conduction. This is rather expected as air is a superb insulator.

Thus, it has been mathematically proven that the best way to keep your coffee warm is to cover it.

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